

Spectrophotometric determination of copper(I) with molybdenum(VI) as a chromogen by molybdenum blue method

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Abstract : A simple, accurate and precise spectrophotometric method was developed by the authors for the determination copper(I) using molybdenum(VI) (ammonium molybdate solution) as a chromogen by molybdenum blue method. During the reaction between copper(I) and ammonium molybdate solution, an instantaneous, stable ink blue color (molybdenum blue) was developed, which showed a wavelength of maximum absorption at 834.8 nm. As a result of such experiments which showed remarkable sensitivity, ammonium molybdate was also used as a reagent for the spot test of copper(I). Beer's law was found to be obeyed up to 1.9798 mg of copper(I) chloride in the solution. Correlation factor was found to be 0.9746. SD and RSD were found to be well within the prescribed limits. The reagent, ammonium molybdate was also used for the photometric determination of copper(I) with good and appreciable results of accuracy. Thus the chromogen molybdenum(VI), can be used for both qualitative and quantitative determination of copper(I) in aqueous/acid media.

Keywords : Copper(I), ammonium molybdate, spectrophotometry, molybdenum blue, photometric titration.

Introduction

Copper exists in I, II and III oxidation states in its compounds and complexes. It is also reported in literature that copper also exhibits of IV and V oxidation states. Though all the compounds of copper have their specific applications, copper(I) finds its importance as a redcutometric reagent and cuprous oxide is extensively employed as fungicide and in seed dressings, anti-fouling paints. Other of compounds and complexes of copper(I) include the colouring of porcelain and glass, oil sweetening process in petroleum industry. Ammoniacal solutions of cuprous chloride are employed for the absorption of even traces of carbon monoxide, which may be present in a gas as an impurity. Copper(I) cyanide is used for copper electroplating¹⁻⁵. The method proposed by authors can be used to ascertain the quality and quantity of these and other such materials containing copper(I) in soluble state. Various methods were described in literature^{6,7} for the quantitative determination of copper(I), copper(II) and copper(III). Copper(I) was quantitatively determined by using different analytical methods such as

potentiometric, volumetric, electro-analytical and spectrophotometric methods. These methods of spectrophotometric estimation of copper(I), use costly reagents and are mostly carried out in non-aqueous media like acetonitrile, chloroform, iso amyl alcohol. The present method given by authors is in aqueous/acid media which is easy, convenient and precise.

During the study of colour reactions between copper(I) solution in 2 M hydrochloric acid medium and different reagents, it was observed by the authors that the aliquot of copper(I) solution with a solution of ammonium molybdate, exhibited an instantaneous, stable ink blue colored product (molybdenum blue⁸), in an overall concentration of 1 N acetic acid medium. This stable ink blue color product showed maximum absorbance at 834.8 nm (Fig. 1). The reaction was not reported by earlier workers in the literature. Since very few reagents are available for the determination of copper(I) and that too in non-aqueous media⁷, the authors attempted this method. Further, since phosphate or phosphoric acid reacts with molybdenum(VI) and reported to be forming "molybde-

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of the ink blue colored product (molybdenum blue) formed during the reaction between copper(I) and molybdenum(VI).

num blue”^{8-10,13} with a reducing agent or with molybdate as phospho-molybdate¹⁰ as pale yellow precipitate, care was taken by the authors to see that use of phosphate or phosphoric acid is avoided everywhere, during the course of experimentation. The reagent molybdenum(VI), was also used by the authors for the photometric determination of copper(I) and in view of sensitivity of detection instantaneously and was also used as a qualitative reagent for the detection of copper(I) by a spot test.

Molybdenum blue¹⁰ is :

- reduced heteropolymolybdate complexes, polyoxometalates containing Mo^V, Mo^{VI}, and a hetero atom such as phosphorus or silicon
- reduced isopolymolybdate complexes, polyoxometalates containing Mo^V, Mo^{VI} formed when solutions of Mo^{VI} are reduced
- a blue pigment containing molybdenum(VI) oxide

Mixed oxide-hydroxide materials called blue oxides are obtained by the reduction of an acidified solution molybdates with Sn^{II} or sulphur dioxide and since they are non-crystalline, structures are not known and the cause of colour is uncertain^{10,11}. The heteropoly-molybdenum blues, are used extensively in analytical chemistry and also as catalysts. The formation of “iso poly-molybdenum blues” which are intense blue in colour, has been used as a sensitive test for reducing reagents. They have recently been shown¹⁰ to contain very large anionic spe-

cies based on the so-called “big wheel” containing 154 Mo atoms, with a formula [Mo₁₅₄O₄₆₂H₁₄(H₂O)₇₀]. This molybdenum blue method is useful in the colorimetric determination of P, As, Si and Ge. The same method is useful for the determination of glucose and drugs containing *o*-hydroquinone by spectrophotometry⁸. Further, “molybdenum blue” was also used for the colorimetric determination of P, As, Si and Ge¹² and for reducing sugars^{8,13}. The phospho-molybdenum blue was obtained by reduction with hydrazine sulphate and extraction with MIBK in organic phase¹⁴. Cobalt(II) was also found to give molybdenum blue and was used as a qualitative test for the detection of molybdenum¹⁵. In view of these results in non-aqueous media, the authors carried out a simple, precise and sensitive method for the qualitative and quantitative determination of copper(I) in aqueous/acid media as molybdenum blue method. The details of the experimentation by authors and results obtained there in are presented in detail in the following sections.

Experimental

Materials :

Copper(I) chloride, 0.1 N solution : It was prepared by dissolving an adequate amount of copper(I) chloride in an overall 2 M hydrochloric acid concentration and was standardized against excess iron(III) and back titration with cerium(IV)¹⁶.

Molybdenum(VI), 0.025 N solution : An adequate amount of ammonium molybdate was weighed and dissolved in required amount of double distilled water and the resulting solution was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask and standardized by oxinate method¹⁷.

All other reagents used were of AnalaR grade only. For the preparation of all the solutions, double distilled water, which was previously boiled and cooled to eliminate dissolved oxygen was used. A Shimadzu UV 260 double beam spectrophotometer with matched set of glass cuvette was used for absorption measurements.

Absorption spectrum of the intense ink blue colored product (molybdenum blue) formed by the reaction between copper(I) and molybdenum(VI) :

An aliquot of copper(I) solution was mixed with 1 ml of 0.0025 N ammonium molybdate solution, to obtain an instantaneous, stable and clear ink blue colored product.

The authors used aqueous or an overall 1 N acetic acid medium for obtaining instantaneous ink blue colour due to the reaction. Since atmospheric or dissolved oxygen tends to oxidize copper(I), great care was taken to eliminate them throughout the experiment. Carbon dioxide was passed through the volumetric flask, distilled water and other solutions to displace air. The mixture was made up to the mark in a 100 ml volumetric flask. The solution of intense ink blue colour was diluted five times and the spectra were taken for an aliquot of the solution with a matched set of cuvettes and it showed a maximum absorbance at 834.8 nm (Fig. 1) in 1 N overall acetic acid medium.

Recommended procedure for the determination of copper(I) using molybdenum(VI) as a chromogen by molybdenum blue method :

In a 25 ml volumetric flask, which was freed from air by passing carbon dioxide, required amount of acetic acid to give an overall 1 N strength, 1.0 ml of 0.025 N ammonium molybdate solution and an aliquot volume of copper(I) solution were added to give an instantaneous, stable ink blue coloured product and the solution was made up to the mark using double distilled water. A portion of such solution was taken into a cuvette and the absorbance of such solution was measured with a matched set of cuvettes. Such an absorbance reading was compared with the standard curve and the amount of copper(I) was determined (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Beer's law obedience plot for the ink blue colored product (molybdenum blue) formed during the reaction between copper(I) and molybdenum(VI) at 834.8 nm.

Recommended procedure for photometric determination of copper(I) using molybdenum(VI) :

In a special titration vessel, 2.5 ml of 0.1 N copper(I) solution, required volume of acetic acid to give an overall concentration of 1 N were mixed and made up to the mark in a 25 ml volumetric flask, through which carbon dioxide was previously passed for 2 min. Absorbance measurements were taken by titrating an aliquot of such a solution with 0.025 N ammonium molybdate solution at a λ_{max} of 834.8 nm. The titration process was performed by continuous stirring in the atmosphere of carbon dioxide. The values of absorbance were plotted against volume of ammonium molybdate solution titrated after making necessary volume correction. The intersection point of the two lines gave the volume of ammonium molybdate solution required to complete the colour reaction with copper(I) taken initially. From such titer value, the amount of copper(I) was determined (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Photometric titration curve for the reaction between copper(I) solution and molybdenum(VI).

Recommended procedure for the spot test determination of copper(I) using molybdenum(VI) by molybdenum blue method :

0.05 ml (one drop) of copper(I) solution in an overall 2 M hydrochloric acid medium and 0.05 ml (one drop) of 0.025 N ammonium molybdate solution were mixed in the cavity of a clean white porcelain spot plate with a clean dry glass rod to give an instantaneous, stable, ink blue colour for the qualitative determination of copper(I) by a spot test. From such experiments the limit of identification was found to be 154.49 γ with a limit of dilution

of 1 : 647.2 for a total volume of 0.1 ml solution. In view of limited number of reagents available for the spot test identification of copper(I) and due to the precision and sensitivity involved, this test by the authors becomes significant. However phosphate or phosphoric acid interfere and great care must be taken to eliminate or avoid them.

Results and discussion

The optical characteristics and validation data reports are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The photometric and titrimetric analyses reports are presented in Table 3. The reaction between copper(I) solution and 0.025 *N* ammonium molybdate solution was instantaneous, stable with a clear ink blue color (molybdenum blue). There was no turbidity or precipitate. The ink blue colored solution showed maximum absorbance at 834.8 nm in an overall concentration of 1 *N* acetic acid. Since ammonium molybdate is colorless, no spectral interference was found. There was no overlap of spectra of other components used. Copper in other oxidation states (other than +1), did not show such a reaction with the specific chromogen, ammonium molybdate solution. The ink blue colored pro-

duct developed was found to be instantaneous and stable for more than 24 h. The interference of foreign metal ions such as Fe^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Sn^{IV}, Ag^I was not found, as such this method can safely be employed for the determination of copper(I) in specific alloys too. Proper care must be taken to avoid phosphate or phosphoric acid as they interfere, forming molybdenum blue¹² or yellow precipitate of phospho-molybdate. Correlation factor was found to be as 0.9746, standard deviation was found to be as 0.36%. LOD was found to be 0.14 mg and LOQ was found to be 0.44 mg. Beer's law was found to be obeyed up to 1.9798 mg of copper(I) in its solutions.

Stability of copper(I) solutions :

In literature¹⁶⁻²⁴ it was found that copper(I) solutions prepared were found to be stable in 2 *N* hydrochloric acid medium. Earlier workers²¹ used aceto nitrile as medium to maintain the stability of copper(I) solution. It was also observed by earlier workers that copper(I) solutions were indefinitely stable in sulphuric acid medium, in a continuous stream of inert atmosphere of carbon dioxide¹⁸. The author studied the stability of copper(I) solutions in phosphoric acid medium as well as in acetic acid medium. It was found by the author that, from 4 *M* overall phosphoric acid strength, the solutions copper(I) were stable up to 16 h even without using carbon dioxide atmosphere. Above 7 *M* overall phosphoric acid medium, a white turbidity and later white precipitate appeared and vanished on further dilution. At lower concentrations of phosphoric acid such as 1.5-3.0 *M*, copper(I) solutions were not quite stable. Similar experiments were carried out by the author in acetic acid medium and in carbon dioxide atmosphere. It was found that, copper(I) solutions are not quite stable in low concentrations of acetic acid and were found to be stable up to 2 h in 4-8 *M* acetic acid medium in carbon dioxide atmosphere. From these observations, the author employed copper(I) solutions prepared in an overall concentration of 2 *M* hydrochloric acid and kept in 6 *M* phosphoric acid, stored in carbon dioxide atmosphere maintains a constant titer up to 16 h. Such solutions of copper(I) were used for redcutometric methods using copper(I) solutions. For the present study, as phosphoric acid interferes in the spectrophotometric

Table 1. Optical characteristics of the ink blue colored product formed by the reaction between copper(I) ammonium molybdate

Parameter	Reported value
Time of reaction	Instantaneous
Product	Clear, no turbidity or precipitate
λ_{max} (nm)	834.8
Beer's law limit (mg/L)	Up to 1.9798 mg of copper(I)
Molar absorptivity ($\text{cm}^{-1} \text{L M}^{-1}$)	230
Correlation coefficient	0.9746
Relative standard deviation (%)	0.36
Limit of detection (mg/L)	0.14
Limit of quantification (mg/L)	0.44

Table 2. Comparative data for the determination of copper(I) by spectrophotometric method with molybdenum(VI) as a chromogenic reagent

Amount of copper(I) determined by standard method ¹² (mg)	Amount of copper(I) determined by author's method (mg)	Relative error (%)
0.4527	0.4469	0.2812
0.6254	0.6261	-0.1119
0.8197	0.8188	0.1097
0.9934	0.9922	0.1207

determination of copper(I) by molybdenum blue method¹³, the author used copper(I) solutions in acetic acid medium, maintained in a carbon dioxide atmosphere.

Study on the reaction in different media :

The reaction between copper(I) and ammonium molybdate solution was studied in different acid media such as hydrochloric acid, sulphuric acid and acetic acid. The reaction was not studied in phosphoric acid medium as it forms molybdenum blue with the reagent used in the method¹³. In hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media, above 0.01 *N*, the faint blue color formed faded away slowly. The reaction was studied in acetic acid medium and it was found that, an instantaneous, stable ink blue color was observed during the reaction between copper(I) and ammonium molybdate in an overall concentration of 1 *N* acetic acid. The effect of time on absorbance measurements with varying concentrations of acetic acid was studied and found that reaction between copper(I) and ammonium molybdate in an overall concentration of 1 *N* acetic acid is instantaneous and quite stable.

Ascertaining optimum conditions for the reaction under study :

In order to ascertain the optimum conditions of acid strength, an aliquot sample of copper(I) is mixed with adequate amount of acetic acid to give varied concentrations of acid strength and mixed with 0.025 *N* ammonium molybdate solution and the absorbance measurements were carried out with varied intervals of time. From such data it was found by the authors that an overall concentration of 1 *N* acetic acid medium is optimum concentration to study the colour reaction between copper(I) and ammonium molybdate.

To ascertain the optimum concentration and volume of the reagent to be added, the author studied the color reaction by varying the concentration and volume of the ammonium molybdate reagent. For each of the concentrated solution of ammonium molybdate, the absorbance values were recorded for every five minutes and continued for one hour. From such results it was found that, 1 ml of 0.025 *N* ammonium molybdate solution was found to be an ideal volume of the chromogen for the present study.

Conclusions

An instantaneous, stable and clear ink blue color (molybdenum blue) was produced by the reaction between copper(I) solution and 0.025 *N* ammonium molybdate solution in aqueous or overall 1 *N* acetic acid medium. There was no turbidity or precipitate. The ink blue colored solution showed a maximum absorbance at 834.8 nm in an overall concentration of 1 *N* acetic acid. Correlation factor was found to be as 0.9746, standard deviation was found to be as 0.36%. LOD was found to be 0.14 mg and LOQ was found to be 0.44 mg. Beer's law is found to be obeyed up to 1.9798 mg of copper(I) chloride in solution. The method developed by the authors was found to be simple, accurate and precise as few methods are only available for the determination of copper(I) in aqueous media and the method developed was very sensitive, precise and accurate for the qualitative as well as quantitative determinations of copper(I) in aqueous/acid media excluding phosphoric acid.

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